

WELL-BEING IN THE TIME OF CORONA:
ASSOCIATIONS OF NEARBY GREENERY
WITH MENTAL WELL-BEING DURING
COVID-19 IN THE NETHERLANDS

Ralitsa Shentova, Sjerp de Vries and Jana Verboom

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIALS

Data Preparation, Additional Results, Questionnaire

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Data Preparation

Incomplete questionnaire responses were excluded, as well as incorrectly filled-in ones, i.e. ones where for the question about which outdoor area attached to their home respondents spent most time in 2020, participants listed an area which does not belong to their home, such as a public park, forest nearby, or allotment garden (this was possible if participants indicated the option “other” and then filled in which area they refer to). Outdoor spaces which belong to the home are henceforth referred to as “private” to distinguish them from the neighbourhood greenery.

For the question of size of the private outdoor area, answers with explanations rather than numbers (e.g. “middelgroot”, “normale grootte voor een achtertuin”) were removed, and remaining responses were log transformed to ensure a more normalised distribution. Then, descriptive results were created for all questions.

Due to the number of responses in each category, the variables for amounts of streetscape and public green areas were recoded into three categories instead of seven. The response options “far too little” and “too little” were put in one category, representing (far) too little amounts, “slightly too little” remained its own category, and response options “neither too much nor too little”, “lightly too much”, “too much”, “far too much” were recoded as one value to represent enough or too much greenery. The recoded variables were used for further analyses.

The responses of the question on frequency of visits to public green areas were transformed to numerical values with estimates for visits per year.

Table 1 shows the estimated annual visits with notes on how they were calculated. 2020 had 366 days in total as it was a leap year, which corresponded to 52 weeks and two days. For calculations, 52 weeks were used.

Table 1. Frequency of visits response options approximate correspondence to number of visits annually.

Response Option	Estimated Annual Visits	Notes
“Almost every day”	312	6 days per week
“A few times a week”	156	3 days per week
“Once a week”	52	-
“A few times a month”	36	3 times per month
“Once a month or less often”	12	Once per month

Additional Results

Participants

In terms of gender, approx. 33% of participants indicated “male”, 66% - “female”, and the rest indicated they prefer not to disclose. Table 2 shows the highest attained level of education of the participants.

Table 2. What is your highest attained level of education?

Response Options	N	%
Primary education	1	0.2%
VMBO-TL of GL, MAVO (MULO)	19	3.6%
HAVO/VWO (HBS, MULO-B, Gymnasium)	36	6.9%
MBO (e.g. MTS, MEAO, UTS)	47	9.0%
LBO (e.g. LTS, LEAO, Huishoudschool, VMBO-BL of KL)	3	0.6%
HBO (e.g. HTS, HEAO, Sociale Academie, Kweekschool, PABO, HAS)	189	36.3%
University degree	224	43.0%
Other, namely...	2	0.4%

In terms of household size, 48% of respondents lived in two-person households, 23% in single-person households, followed by households with four people and three people, with 12 and 10% of respondents, respectively. Approximately 18% had a dog and 18% had a child/children in the household. The table below illustrates the working situation of respondents.

Table 3. What describes your situation for most of the year since March 2020? (Multiple responses possible. Please tick what is most strongly applicable.).

In retirement	Working from home	Working outside home	Stay-at-home parent/homemaker	Following education	Unemployed
157	259	148	82	61	33

Private Outdoor Space

The table below illustrates that kinds of private outdoor spaces participants had.

Table 4. Which of the following outdoor spaces belong to your home? (multiple responses possible; N=521)

Own garden	Balcony	Roof terrace	Gallery / balcony shared with other households	Closed courtyard shared with other households	Private courtyard/patio	Public courtyard	Other	No green area attached to home
421	103	34	19	18	18	19	19	16

Out of those respondents (who have a green space attached to their home, n=505), 82% spent the most time in their private garden(s), followed by balcony (9% of respondents).

What is the approximate size of this space in m²?

N=498 (removed outliers and unclear explanations)

Range: 1-150000 m², mean = 431, median = 70, SD = 1476

How often have you been here in your spare time this year (2020)? - Almost never:Very often

Majority of respondents visiting often (last three points on 7-point scale, 81%)

Characteristics of the greenery:

Figure 1. Private outdoor space - greenness and pavement.

There was a negative correlation between how paved and how vegetated the space is, $r(414)=-.67$, $p<.001$. This makes sense – if the space is more paved, then there is likely less vegetation visible. This variable is referred to as “greenness” in the manuscript.

How much of the following types of vegetation do you normally see throughout the year when you are in this space (including vegetation outside the space itself, if visible)?

Figure 2. Private outdoor space - abundance of different types of vegetation.

Throughout the year in this space, do you see: Very few plant and tree species - Very many plant and tree species / Very few bird species – Very many bird species

Figure 3. Private outdoor space –diversity.

What do you think of the birds that you can observe in or from this space?

89% of respondents found the birds mostly attractive to see or hear

How much of the time that you spent in this space did you engage in gardening?

Figure 4. Private outdoor space - time spent gardening.

Most respondents spent less than half of the time gardening when they were in this space.

Do you think of gardening as a pleasant or unpleasant activity? - Very unpleasant:Very pleasant

76% think of gardening as a pleasant activity (last three points of 7-point Likert scale).

Neighbourhood Greenery

How often did visit public green areas in your neighbourhood this year (2020)?

Table 5. Neighbourhood green areas - frequency of visits.

Almost every day	A few times a week	Once a week	A few times a month	Once a month or less often	Never
35.9	30.3	14.4	8.3	8.1	3.1

Overall, how satisfied are you with the: Public green areas / Streetscape greenery in your neighbourhood?

Figure 5. Neighbourhood greenery - satisfaction.

What do you think of the amount of: Streetscape greenery / Public green areas in your neighbourhood?

Figure 6. Neighbourhood greenery - amounts.

The streetscape greenery in my neighbourhood is:

Figure 7. Streetscape greenery quality.

The public green areas in my neighbourhood are:

Figure 8. Public green areas quality.

Additionally, 81% of respondents felt the public green areas in their neighbourhood were safe (last three points in 7-point Likert scale).

How would you describe the view from your living room (or the room where you spend most of your time during the day while at home) throughout the year?

Figure 9. View from the living room greenness.

Correlation Tables

Table 6. Descriptive statistics and correlations for main study variables – garden.

Variable	N	M	SD	1.	2.	3.	4.	5.	6.	7.	8.	9.
1. GHQ	421	2.99	0.46	-								
2. Size	416	2.05	0.61	.18**	-							
3. Frequency of Contact	421	5.92	1.34	.18**	.39**	-						
4. Diversity Plants	421	5.58	1.35	.19**	.37**	.42**	-					
5. Diversity Birds	421	4.93	1.45	.13**	.39**	.36**	.56**	-				
6. Gardening Time	421	3.40	1.14	-.01	.24**	.23**	.24**	.19**	-			
7. NR	421	4.10	0.69	.02	.09	.12**	.15**	.15**	.11*	-		

8. Greenness	421	5.93	1.18	.15**	.42**	.39**	.59**	.46**	.25**	.16**	-	
9. Window View Greenness	421	5.06	1.79	.18**	.38**	.28**	.41**	.44**	-.10*	.08	.32**	-

* $p < .05$. ** $p < .01$.
 N = 416

Table 7. Descriptive statistics and correlations for main study variables – public green spaces.

Variable	M	SD	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1. GHQ	2.96	0.48	-						
2. Streetscape Amount	1.19	.86	.10*	-					
3. Public Areas Amount	1.46	.76	.09*	.55**	-				
4. Streetscape Quality	4.33	1.36	.17**	.57**	.42**	-			
5. Public Areas Quality	5.01	1.15	.13**	.30**	.50**	.58**	-		
6. Frequency of Visits	170.71	117.09	.08	.09*	.09	.12**	.21**	-	
7. View Greenness	4.76	1.92	.18**	.35**	.20**	.28**	.20**	.12**	-
8. NR	4.07	0.69	.04	-.03	-.12**	-.01	.05	.06	.13**

* $p < .05$. ** $p < .01$.
 N = 521

The annual frequency of visits to public green areas was not correlated to the frequency of contact with a garden (N=421). There was a very low, if any (linear), correlation between it with a private outdoor area, $r(505) = .096$, $p < .05$.

PROCESS Outputs

Garden Features & Frequency of Contact, Time Spent Gardening

PROCESS Procedure for SPSS Version 4.1	PROCESS Procedure for SPSS Version 4.1																																																								
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OUTCOME VARIABLE:

GFreq

Model Summary

R	R-sq	MSE	F	df1	df2	p
.5012	.2512	1.3526	69.2816	2.0000	413.0000	.0000

Model

	coeff	se	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
constant	2.8136	.2703	10.4079	.0000	2.2822	3.3450
Size_log	.5770	.1004	5.7502	.0000	.3798	.7743
PlantDiv	.3421	.0460	7.4427	.0000	.2518	.4325

OUTCOME VARIABLE:

GHQ

Model Summary

R	R-sq	MSE	F	df1	df2	p
.2639	.0696	.1975	7.6893	4.0000	411.0000	.0000

Model

	coeff	se	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
constant	2.4387	.1171	20.8214	.0000	2.2084	2.6689
Size_log	.0826	.0402	2.0556	.0405	.0036	.1617
GTime	-.0384	.0200	-1.9217	.0553	-.0778	.0009
GFreq	.0320	.0189	1.6929	.0912	-.0052	.0692
PlantDiv	.0521	.0188	2.7660	.0059	.0151	.0892

***** TOTAL EFFECT MODEL *****

OUTCOME VARIABLE:

GHQ

OUTCOME VARIABLE:

GFreq

Model Summary

R	R-sq	MSE	F	df1	df2	p
.5012	.2512	1.3526	69.2816	2.0000	413.0000	.0000

Model

	coeff	se	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
constant	2.8136	.2703	10.4079	.0000	2.2822	3.3450
PlantDiv	.3421	.0460	7.4427	.0000	.2518	.4325
Size_log	.5770	.1004	5.7502	.0000	.3798	.7743

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GTime	-.0384	.0200	-1.9217	.0553	-.0778	.0009
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Size_log	.0826	.0402	2.0556	.0405	.0036	.1617

***** TOTAL EFFECT MODEL *****

OUTCOME VARIABLE:

GHQ

Model Summary

R	R-sq	MSE	F	df1	df2	p
.2371	.0562	.1993	12.3026	2.0000	413.0000	.0000

Model

	coeff	se	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
constant	2.4871	.1038	23.9662	.0000	2.2831	2.6911
Size_log	.0886	.0385	2.2997	.0220	.0129	.1643
PlantDiv	.0572	.0176	3.2438	.0013	.0226	.0919

***** TOTAL, DIRECT, AND INDIRECT EFFECTS OF X ON Y *****

Total effect of X on Y

Effect	se	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
.0886	.0385	2.2997	.0220	.0129	.1643

Direct effect of X on Y

Effect	se	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
.0826	.0402	2.0556	.0405	.0036	.1617

Indirect effect(s) of X on Y:

	Effect	BootSE	BootLLCI	BootULCI
TOTAL	.0060	.0144	-.0213	.0350
GTime	-.0125	.0081	-.0300	.0012
GFreq	.0185	.0121	-.0043	.0434

***** ANALYSIS NOTES AND ERRORS *****

Level of confidence for all confidence intervals in output:
95.0000

Number of bootstrap samples for percentile bootstrap confidence intervals:
5000

----- END MATRIX -----

Model Summary

R	R-sq	MSE	F	df1	df2	p
.2371	.0562	.1993	12.3026	2.0000	413.0000	.0000

Model

	coeff	se	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
constant	2.4871	.1038	23.9662	.0000	2.2831	2.6911
PlantDiv	.0572	.0176	3.2438	.0013	.0226	.0919
Size_log	.0886	.0385	2.2997	.0220	.0129	.1643

***** TOTAL, DIRECT, AND INDIRECT EFFECTS OF X ON Y *****

Total effect of X on Y

Effect	se	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
.0572	.0176	3.2438	.0013	.0226	.0919

Direct effect of X on Y

Effect	se	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
.0521	.0188	2.7660	.0059	.0151	.0892

Indirect effect(s) of X on Y:

	Effect	BootSE	BootLLCI	BootULCI
TOTAL	.0051	.0081	-.0097	.0227
GTime	-.0059	.0039	-.0146	.0005
GFreq	.0110	.0073	-.0021	.0267

***** ANALYSIS NOTES AND ERRORS *****

Level of confidence for all confidence intervals in output:
95.0000

Number of bootstrap samples for percentile bootstrap confidence intervals:
5000

----- END MATRIX -----

Public Green Areas & Frequency of Visits

***** PROCESS Procedure for SPSS Version 4.1 *****

Written by Andrew F. Hayes, Ph.D. www.afhayes.com
Documentation available in Hayes (2022). www.guilford.com/p/hayes3

Model : 4
Y : GHQ
X : PubQual
M : PubFreq

Sample
Size: 521

OUTCOME VARIABLE:
PubFreq

Model Summary

R	R-sq	MSE	F	df1	df2	p
.2073	.0430	13145.2246	23.3006	1.0000	519.0000	.0000

Model

	coeff	se	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
constant	64.8345	22.5031	2.8811	.0041	20.6262	109.0429
PubQual	21.1183	4.3750	4.8271	.0000	12.5235	29.7131

OUTCOME VARIABLE:
GHQ

Model Summary

R	R-sq	MSE	F	df1	df2	p
.1367	.0187	.2239	4.9329	2.0000	518.0000	.0075

Model

	coeff	se	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
constant	2.6846	.0936	28.6774	.0000	2.5007	2.8685
PubQual	.0475	.0185	2.5755	.0103	.0113	.0838
PubFreq	.0002	.0002	1.2250	.2211	-.0001	.0006

***** TOTAL EFFECT MODEL *****

OUTCOME VARIABLE:
GHQ

Model Summary

R	R-sq	MSE	F	df1	df2	p
.1259	.0158	.2241	8.3570	1.0000	519.0000	.0040

Model

	coeff	se	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
constant	2.6990	.0929	29.0468	.0000	2.5164	2.8815
PubQual	.0522	.0181	2.8908	.0040	.0167	.0877

***** TOTAL, DIRECT, AND INDIRECT EFFECTS OF X ON Y *****

Total effect of X on Y

Effect	se	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
.0522	.0181	2.8908	.0040	.0167	.0877

Direct effect of X on Y

Effect	se	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
.0475	.0185	2.5755	.0103	.0113	.0838

Indirect effect(s) of X on Y:

	Effect	BootSE	BootLLCI	BootULCI
PubFreq	.0047	.0043	-.0034	.0134

***** ANALYSIS NOTES AND ERRORS *****

Level of confidence for all confidence intervals in output:
95.0000

Number of bootstrap samples for percentile bootstrap confidence intervals:
5000

----- END MATRIX -----

Questionnaire

Information

Participants could indicate their preferred language at the start and the survey continued in the chosen language. The final block on Address was used for a part of the initial aims of the master thesis which this research was conducted for. The responses to it were too few, so were not used in further analyses and were separated from the other data.

Questionnaire (English and Dutch together)

Start of Block: Intro

Q1 Please choose your preferred language in the top right corner. Kies de taal van uw voorkeur rechts boven.

Welcome to this survey! This research aims to examine the relationship between greenery in the residential environment and well-being. It is part of a master thesis at Wageningen University and Research (WUR). For any questions, you can contact the researcher, master student Ralitsa Shentova at ralitsa.shentova@wur.nl.

In this survey, you will be asked to answer questions on greenery in your residential environment, your living situation, and your well-being before and after the COVID-19 pandemic reached the Netherlands (roughly considered as March 2020). This will take around 10 minutes. We handle the information you provide with great care. Responses are treated confidentially, stored securely and accessible only to researchers at WUR involved in this project.

By proceeding, you confirm that you understand that:

- Your contribution will be confidential;
- Your participation is entirely voluntary;
- You are free to exit the survey at any time by closing the browser window;
- The data will be retained in secure storage.

Q1 Please choose your preferred language in the top right corner. Kies de taal van uw voorkeur rechts boven.

Welkom bij deze enquête! In dit onderzoek wordt gekeken naar de relatie tussen groen in de woonomgeving en welzijn. Het maakt deel uit van een scriptie van Wageningen University and Research (WUR). Mocht u vragen hebben, dan kunt u contact opnemen met de onderzoeker, MSc studente Ralitsa Shentova via ralitsa.shentova@wur.nl.

In deze enquête worden u vragen gesteld over het groen in uw woonomgeving, uw woonsituatie en uw welzijn voor en nadat de COVID-19-pandemie Nederland bereikte (grootweg maart 2020). Dit vraagt ongeveer 10 minuten van uw tijd. We gaan zorgvuldig om met de door u verstrekte informatie. Uw antwoorden worden vertrouwelijk behandeld, veilig opgeslagen en zijn alleen toegankelijk voor onderzoekers van de WUR die bij dit project betrokken zijn.

Door verder te gaan, geeft u aan dat u begrijpt dat:

- uw gegevens vertrouwelijk worden behandeld;
- uw deelname geheel vrijwillig is;
- u de enquête op elk moment kunt verlaten door de browser te sluiten;
- de verstrekte gegevens veilig worden opgeslagen;

Q2 If you are currently living in the Netherlands, at least 18 years old, and agree to participate, please click on the arrow to continue.

Q2 Indien u momenteel in Nederland woont, minimaal 18 jaar oud bent, en bereid bent deel te nemen, klik op de pijl om verder te gaan.

End of Block: Intro

Start of Block: Residential green spaces – home

Q4 In this section, you will be asked a set of questions about your access to and use of green spaces, starting with those closest to your home.

Q4 In deze sectie wordt u een aantal vragen gesteld over uw toegang tot en gebruik van groen, te beginnen met dat het dichtst bij uw huis.

Q3 Which of the following outdoor spaces belong to your home?

- Own garden
- Balcony
- Roof terrace
- Gallery / balcony shared with other households
- Closed courtyard shared with other households
- Private courtyard / patio
- Public courtyard
- Other, please specify ... _____
- No outside space

Q3 Welke buitenruimte hoort er bij uw woning?

Er zijn meerdere antwoorden mogelijk. Kruis alle opties aan die van toepassing zijn.

- Eigen tuin
- Balkon
- Dakterras
- Galerij/balkon gedeeld met andere huishoudens
- Gezamenlijke afgesloten binnentuin of hofje

- Patio/eigen binnentuin
- Openbare binnentuin of hofje
- Anders, namelijk: _____
- Geen buitenruimte

Skip To: End of Block If Q3 = No outside space

Carry Forward Selected Choices - Entered Text from "Q3"

Q5 Since the start of the nationwide pandemic measures in the Netherlands in March 2020, which one of these have you spent most time in?

- Own garden
- Balcony
- Roof terrace
- Gallery / balcony shared with other households
- Closed courtyard shared with other households
- Private courtyard / patio
- Public courtyard
- Other, please specify ...

Q5 In welke van deze buitenruimtes heeft u sinds de start van de coronamaatregelen in Nederland in maart 2020 de meeste tijd doorgebracht?

- Eigen tuin
- Balkon
- Dakterras
- Galerij/balkon gedeeld met andere huishoudens
- Gezamenlijke afgesloten binnentuin of hofje

- Patio/eigen binnentuin
- Openbare binnentuin of hofje
- Anders, namelijk:

Q9 What is the approximate size of this space in m²? *In the case of a garden, if you have both front and back gardens, consider the one you spend most time in.*

Q9 Wat is ongeveer de grootte van deze ruimte (in m²)? *In het geval van een tuin, als u zowel een voor- als een achtertuin heeft, neem dan de tuin waar u de meeste tijd doorbrengt.*

Q8 Please answer the following questions thinking of this most used outdoor space.

Q8 Ga bij het beantwoorden van de volgende vragen uit van deze meest gebruikte buitenruimte.

Q6 How often have you been here in your spare time this year (2020)?

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
Almost never	<input type="radio"/>	Very often						

Q6 Hoe vaak bent u hier dit jaar in uw vrije tijd te vinden geweest?

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
Vrijwel nooit	<input type="radio"/>	Heel vaak						

Q49 Compared to previous years (without a COVID-19 pandemic), did you spend less or more time in this space this year?

- Less than before
- As much as before

More than before

Q49 Bracht u in vergelijking met voorgaande jaren, zonder COVID-19-pandemie, dit jaar minder of meer tijd door in deze buitenruimte?

Minder dan voorheen

Evenveel als voorheen

Meer dan voorheen

Q55 To what extent is this outdoor space sealed (e.g. paved)?

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
Not at all	<input type="radio"/>	Completely paved						

Q55 In welke mate is deze buitenruimte verhard (bijv. betegeld of bestraat)?

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
Helemaal niet	<input type="radio"/>	Compleet verhard						

Q10 How much vegetation is there in this space (e.g. trees, grass, shrubs)?

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
None at all	<input type="radio"/>	Quite a lot						

Q10 Hoeveel groen is er aanwezig in deze buitenruimte zelf (planten, bomen, gras, struiken)?

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
Helemaal geen	<input type="radio"/>	Heel veel						

Q11 How much of the following types of vegetation do you normally see throughout the year when you are in this space (including vegetation outside the space itself, if visible)?

	None at all	A little	A moderate amount	A lot	A great deal
Grass	<input type="radio"/>				
Flowers, herbs	<input type="radio"/>				
Shrubs	<input type="radio"/>				
Trees	<input type="radio"/>				

Q11 Hoeveel van elk van de volgende soorten groen ziet u normaal gesproken door het jaar heen wanneer u in deze buitenruimte bent (inclusief groen buiten de ruimte zelf, indien zichtbaar)?

	Helemaal niet	Een beetje	Redelijk wat	Veel	Heel veel
Gras	<input type="radio"/>				
Bloemen, kruiden	<input type="radio"/>				
Struiken	<input type="radio"/>				
Bomen	<input type="radio"/>				

Q12 Throughout the year in this space, do you see:

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
Very few plant and tree species	<input type="radio"/>	Very many plant and tree species						
Very few bird species	<input type="radio"/>	Very many bird species						

Q12 Ziet u als u in deze buitenruimte bent door het jaar heen...

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
	<input type="radio"/>						

Heel weinig
verschillende
soorten
groen

Heel veel
verschillende
soorten
groen

Heel weinig
verschillende
soorten
vogels

Heel veel
verschillende
soorten
vogels

Q13 What do you think of the birds that you can observe in or from this space?

- Mostly attractive to see or hear
- Mix of attractive and unattractive to see or hear
- Mostly unattractive to see or hear

Q13 Wat vindt u van de vogels die u in of vanuit deze ruimte kunt waarnemen?

- De meeste zijn leuk om te zien of te horen
- Het is een mix van leuk en niet leuk om te zien of te horen
- De meeste zijn niet leuk om te zien of te horen

Q14 How much of the time that you spent in this space did you engage in gardening?

- Almost all the time
- More than half the time
- About half the time
- Less than half the time
- Almost no time

Q14 Hoeveel van de tijd dat u in deze ruimte bent, besteedt u aan tuinieren?

- Bijna alle tijd
- Meer dan de helft van de tijd

- Ongeveer de helft van de tijd
- Minder dan de helft van de tijd
- Vrijwel geen tijd

Q15 Do you think of gardening as a pleasant or unpleasant activity?

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
Very unpleasant	<input type="radio"/>	Very pleasant						

Q15 Vindt u tuinieren een onaangename of aangename bezigheid?

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
Heel onaangenaam	<input type="radio"/>	Heel aangenaam						

End of Block: Residential green spaces – home

Start of Block: Residential green spaces - neighbourhood

Q36 In this survey, we distinguish two types of green areas:

Streetscape greenery: all greenery that you see on the street, incl. trees, lawns, hedges, part of a park that can be seen from the street, and also greenery belonging to private gardens that you can see from the street.

Public green areas: publicly accessible green areas, e.g. parks, public gardens, woodlands which paths running through them, lawns and grassy playing fields. Exception: a privately owned garden does not count, because it's not publicly accessible.

Q36 In de vragenlijst maken we een onderscheid tussen twee soorten groen:

Straatgroen: al het groen dat je in de straat ziet. Daarbij kan het gaan om bomen, grasbermen en groenstroken, maar ook om het gedeelte van een park dat vanaf de straat is te zien. Ook het groen in privétuinen dat je vanaf de straat kunt zien, telt mee.

Openbare groengebieden: groen in de vorm van openbaar toegankelijke groengebieden (waar je in kunt). Denk aan parken, plantsoenen en bosjes waar een pad doorheen loopt, gras- en speelveldjes, etc. NB: een eigen tuin telt niet mee, want die is niet openbaar.

Q37 What do you think of the amount of:

	Far too little	Too little	Slightly too little	Neither too much nor too little	Slightly too much	Too much	Far too much

Streetscape greenery in your neighbourhood	<input type="radio"/>						
Public green areas in your neighbourhood	<input type="radio"/>						

Q37 Wat vindt u van de hoeveelheid...

	Veel te weinig	Te weinig	Iets te weinig	Niet te veel en niet te weinig	Iets te veel	Te veel	Veel te veel
Straatgroen bij u in de buurt?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Openbare groengebieden bij u in de buurt?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Q48 When answering the following questions, please consider the green areas throughout the year, not only in the current winter season.

Q48 Denk bij het beantwoorden van de volgende vragen niet alleen aan het huidige winterseizoen, maar aan het groen door het jaar heen.

Q39 The streetscape greenery in my neighbourhood is:

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
Very monotonous	<input type="radio"/>	Very varied						
Very poorly maintained	<input type="radio"/>	Very well maintained						
Very unattractive	<input type="radio"/>	Very attractive						

Q39 Het straatgroen in mijn buurt is:

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
	<input type="radio"/>						

Heel eentonig	<input type="radio"/>	Heel gevarieerd						
Heel slecht onderhouden	<input type="radio"/>	Heel goed onderhouden						
Heel onaantrekkelijk	<input type="radio"/>	Heel aantrekkelijk						

Q40 The public green areas in my neighbourhood are:

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
Very unsafe	<input type="radio"/>	Very safe						
Very monotonous	<input type="radio"/>	Very varied						
Very poorly maintained	<input type="radio"/>	Very well maintained						
Very unattractive	<input type="radio"/>	Very attractive						
Lacking amenities (e.g. benches, sports equipment)	<input type="radio"/>	Very well-equipped						

Q40 De openbare groengebieden in mijn buurt zijn:

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
Heel onveilig	<input type="radio"/>	Heel veilig						
Heel eentonig	<input type="radio"/>	Heel gevarieerd						
Heel slecht onderhouden	<input type="radio"/>	Heel goed onderhouden						
Heel onaantrekkelijk	<input type="radio"/>	Heel aantrekkelijk						
Heel slecht uitgerust qua voorzieningen	<input type="radio"/>	Heel goed uitgerust qua voorzieningen						

(bijvoorbeeld
banken, sport- en
speelvoorzieningen)

Q41 Overall, how satisfied are you with the:

	Extremely dissatisfied	Dissatisfied	Slightly dissatisfied	Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied	Slightly satisfied	Satisfied	Extremely satisfied
Streetscape greenery in your neighbourhood	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Public green areas in your neighbourhood	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Q41 Hoe tevreden bent u, alles bij elkaar genomen, over het:

	Ze er ontevrede n	Ontevrede n	Enigszin ontevrede n	Niet tevreden maar ook niet ontevrede n	Enigszin s tevrede n	Tevrede n	Ze er tevrede n
Straatgroen bij u in de buurt?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Openbare groengebiede n bij u in de buurt?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Q42 How often did visit public green areas in your neighbourhood this year (2020)?

- Almost every day
- A few times a week
- Once a week
- A few times a month

Once a month or less often

Never

Q42 Hoe vaak bezocht u dit jaar (2020) openbare groengebieden in uw buurt?

Bijna elke dag

Een paar keer per week

Een keer per week

Een paar keer per maand

Een keer per maand of minder vaak

Nooit

Skip To: Q44 If Q42 = Never

Q51 Compared to previous years (without a COVID-19 pandemic), did you spend less or more time in this space this year?

Less than before

As much as before

More than before

Q51 Bracht u dit jaar (2020) in vergelijking met vóór de COVID-19-pandemie minder of meer tijd door in het openbare groen in uw buurt?

Minder dan voorheen

Evenveel als voorheen

Meer dan voorheen

Q44 How would you describe the view from your living room (or the room where you spend most of your time during the day while at home) throughout the year?

1

2

3

4

5

6

7

Mostly built-up/stony	<input type="radio"/>	Mostly vegetated						
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Q44 Hoe zou u het uitzicht vanuit uw woonkamer (of de kamer waar u de meeste tijd thuis doorbrengt) het hele jaar door omschrijven?

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
Voornamelijk bebouwd/stenig	<input type="radio"/>	Voornamelijk groen (vegetatie)						

End of Block: Residential green spaces - neighbourhood

Start of Block: GHQ-12

Q53 As mentioned, this study examines the relationship between greenery in the residential environment and well-being. The following questions are related to well-being.

Q53

Zoals eerder vermeld, willen we met deze studie de relatie tussen groen in de woonomgeving en uw welzijn onderzoeken. De volgende vragen gaan over uw welzijn.

Q50 Since the COVID-19 pandemic reached the Netherlands (consider March 2020 when measures began to be implemented nationally), have you:

Been able to concentrate on what you're doing?	<input type="radio"/> Better than before	<input type="radio"/> Same as before	<input type="radio"/> Less than before	<input type="radio"/> Much less than before
Lost much sleep over worry?	<input type="radio"/> Not at all	<input type="radio"/> No more than before	<input type="radio"/> Rather more than before	<input type="radio"/> Much more than before
Felt you were playing a useful part in things?	<input type="radio"/> More so than before	<input type="radio"/> Same as before	<input type="radio"/> Less useful from before	<input type="radio"/> Much less useful than before
Felt capable of making decisions about things?	<input type="radio"/> More so than before	<input type="radio"/> Same as before	<input type="radio"/> Less so than before	<input type="radio"/> Much less capable than before
Felt constantly under strain?	<input type="radio"/> Not at all	<input type="radio"/> No more than before	<input type="radio"/> Rather more than before	<input type="radio"/> Much more than before

Felt you couldn't overcome your difficulties?	<input type="radio"/> Not at all	<input type="radio"/> No more than before	<input type="radio"/> Rather more than before	<input type="radio"/> Much more than before
Been able to enjoy your normal day-to-day activities?	<input type="radio"/> More so than before	<input type="radio"/> Same as before	<input type="radio"/> Less so than before	<input type="radio"/> Much less than before
Been able to face up to your problems?	<input type="radio"/> More so than before	<input type="radio"/> Same as before	<input type="radio"/> Less so than before	<input type="radio"/> Much less than before
Been feeling unhappy and depressed?	<input type="radio"/> Not at all	<input type="radio"/> No more than before	<input type="radio"/> Rather more than before	<input type="radio"/> Much more than before
Been losing confidence in yourself?	<input type="radio"/> Not at all	<input type="radio"/> No more than before	<input type="radio"/> Rather more than before	<input type="radio"/> Much more than before
Been thinking of yourself as a worthless person?	<input type="radio"/> Not at all	<input type="radio"/> No more than before	<input type="radio"/> Rather more than before	<input type="radio"/> Much more than before
Been feeling reasonably happy, all things considered?	<input type="radio"/> More so than before	<input type="radio"/> About the same as before	<input type="radio"/> Less so than before	<input type="radio"/> Much less than before

Q50 Sinds de COVID-19 pandemie Nederland bereikte (denk aan maart 2020 toen de eerste maatregelen landelijk ingevoerd werden):

Hebt u zich kunnen concentreren op uw bezigheden?	<input type="radio"/> Beter dan voorheen	<input type="radio"/> Net zo goed als voorheen	<input type="radio"/> Minder goed dan voorheen	<input type="radio"/> Veel minder goed dan voorheen
Bent u door zorgen veel slaap tekort gekomen?	<input type="radio"/> Helemaal niet	<input type="radio"/> Niet meer dan voorheen	<input type="radio"/> Iets meer dan voorheen	<input type="radio"/> Veel meer dan voorheen
Hebt u het gevoel gehad nuttig bezig te zijn geweest?	<input type="radio"/> Meer dan voorheen	<input type="radio"/> Hetzelfde als voorheen	<input type="radio"/> Minder dan voorheen	<input type="radio"/> Veel minder dan voorheen

Hebt u zich in staat gevoeld goede beslissingen te nemen?	<input type="radio"/> Meer dan voorheen	<input type="radio"/> Hetzelfde als voorheen	<input type="radio"/> Minder dan voorheen	<input type="radio"/> Veel minder dan voorheen
Hebt u het gevoel gehad voortdurend onder druk te staan?	<input type="radio"/> Helemaal niet	<input type="radio"/> Niet meer dan voorheen	<input type="radio"/> Iets meer dan voorheen	<input type="radio"/> Veel meer dan voorheen
Hebt u het gevoel gehad dat u uw moeilijkheden niet de baas kon?	<input type="radio"/> Helemaal niet	<input type="radio"/> Niet meer dan voorheen	<input type="radio"/> Iets meer dan voorheen	<input type="radio"/> Veel meer dan voorheen
Hebt u plezier kunnen beleven aan uw gewone, dagelijkse bezigheden?	<input type="radio"/> Meer dan voorheen	<input type="radio"/> Hetzelfde als voorheen	<input type="radio"/> Minder dan voorheen	<input type="radio"/> Veel minder dan voorheen
Bent u in staat geweest uw problemen onder ogen te zien?	<input type="radio"/> Meer dan voorheen	<input type="radio"/> Hetzelfde als voorheen	<input type="radio"/> Minder dan voorheen	<input type="radio"/> Veel minder dan voorheen
Hebt u zich ongelukkig en neerslachtig gevoeld?	<input type="radio"/> Helemaal niet	<input type="radio"/> Niet meer dan voorheen	<input type="radio"/> Iets meer dan voorheen	<input type="radio"/> Veel meer dan voorheen
Bent u het vertrouwen in uzelf kwijtgeraakt?	<input type="radio"/> Helemaal niet	<input type="radio"/> Niet meer dan voorheen	<input type="radio"/> Iets meer dan voorheen	<input type="radio"/> Veel meer dan voorheen
Hebt u zich als persoon niets waard gevoeld?	<input type="radio"/> Helemaal niet	<input type="radio"/> Niet meer dan voorheen	<input type="radio"/> Iets meer dan voorheen	<input type="radio"/> Veel meer dan voorheen
Hebt u zich alles bij elkaar redelijk gelukkig gevoeld?	<input type="radio"/> Meer dan voorheen	<input type="radio"/> Ongeveer hetzelfde als voorheen	<input type="radio"/> Minder dan voorheen	<input type="radio"/> Veel minder dan voorheen

End of Block: GHQ-12

Start of Block: NC-6

Q19 You are almost at the end of the survey! We will only ask a few more questions ask about your attitude towards nature, your living situation and other background characteristics.

Q19 U bent bijna aan het einde van de enquête. Wij stellen nog enkele vragen over uw houding ten aanzien van natuur, uw woonsituatie en andere achtergrondkenmerken.

Q20 For each of the following, please rate the extent to which you agree with each statement. Please respond as you really feel, rather than how you think “most people” feel.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither disagree nor agree	Agree	Strongly agree
My ideal vacation spot would be a remote, wilderness area.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I always think about how my actions affect the environment.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
My connection to nature and the environment is a part of my spirituality.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I take notice of living nature wherever I am.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
My relationship to nature is an important part of who I am.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I feel very connected to all living things and the earth.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Q20 Geef voor elk van de volgende stellingen aan in hoeverre u het hiermee eens bent. Reageer alstublieft zoals u het zelf ziet, en niet zoals u denkt dat “de meeste mensen” het zien.

	Helemaal niet mee eens	Niet mee eens	Niet mee eens en niet mee oneens	Mee eens	Helemaal mee eens

Mijn ideale vakantieplek is een afgelegen gebied, een wildernis.

Ik denk altijd na over hoe mijn gedrag het milieu beïnvloedt.

Mijn verbinding met de natuur en de omgeving maakt deel uit van mijn spiritualiteit.

Ik heb een oog voor de levende natuur, waar ik ook ben.

Mijn relatie met de natuur is een belangrijk deel van wie ik ben.

Ik voel me sterk verbonden met alle levende wezens en de aarde.

End of Block: NC-6

Start of Block: Household

Q21 How many people live in your household?

Q21 Uit hoeveel personen bestaat uw huishouden?

Q22 Are there any children (under 18 years old) in your household?

Yes

No

Q22 Zijn er kinderen (onder 18 jaar oud) in uw huishouden aanwezig?

Ja

Nee

Display This Question:

If Q22 = Yes

Q23 What is the age of the youngest child?

Q23 Wat is de leeftijd van het jongste kind?

Q24 Is there a dog in the household?

Yes

No

Q24 Is er een hond in het huishouden aanwezig?

Ja

Nee

End of Block: Household

Start of Block: Demographics

Q25 What is your gender?

Male

Female

Other gender identity

Prefer not to disclose

Q25 Wat is uw geslacht?

Man

Vrouw

Anders

Wil ik niet zeggen

Q26 Which age group do you belong to?

18-34

35-64

65+

Q26 In welke leeftijdscategorie valt u?

18-34

35-64

65+

Q47 What is your highest attained level of education?

No training (primary education not completed)

Primary education

VMBO-TL of GL, MAVO (MULO)

HAVO/VWO (HBS, MULO-B, Gymnasium)

MBO (e.g. MTS, MEAO, UTS)

LBO (e.g. LTS, LEAO, Huishoudschool, VMBO-BL of KL)

HBO (e.g. HTS, HEAO, Sociale Academie, Kweekschool, PABO, HAS)

University degree

Other, namely... _____

Q47 Wat is uw hoogst voltooide opleiding?

Geen opleiding (lager onderwijs niet afgemaakt)

Basisonderwijs (lagere school)

VMBO-TL of GL, MAVO (MULO)

HAVO/VWO (HBS, MULO-B, Gymnasium)

MBO (bijv. MTS, MEAO, UTS)

LBO (bijv. LTS, LEAO, Huishoudschool, VMBO-BL of KL)

HBO (bijv. HTS, HEAO, Sociale Academie, Kweekschool, PABO, HAS)

Wetenschappelijk onderwijs (universiteit)

Anders, namelijk... _____

Q27 What describes your situation for most of the year since March 2020?

Multiple answers are possible. Please tick what is most strongly applicable.

In retirement

Working from home, ... hours per week (*please fill in*)

Working outside home, ... hours per week (*please fill in*)

Stay-at-home parent / homemaker

Following education

Unemployed

Q27 Wat beschrijft uw situatie gedurende het grootste deel van het jaar sinds maart 2020?
Er zijn meerdere antwoorden mogelijk. Kruis de opties aan die sterk van toepassing zijn.

- Met pensioen (AOW, VUT, FPU)
- Vanuit huis werken, _____ uur per week (vul in)

- Buitenshuis werken, _____ uur per week (vul in)

- Huisvrouw/-man
- Onderwijs volgen / studeren
- Werkloos

Page Break

End of Block: Demographics

Start of Block: Address

Q28 In this study, we are examining the relationship between greenery in the residential environment and well-being. In order to be more precise on the exact amount greenery in your area, we can use spatial data based on aerial imagery. Only for this reason, we ask for your exact address. As this is privacy-sensitive information, we take extra security measures. This information will be stored separately from the other responses and linked briefly only to retrieve the aerial image data which we use for analysis. You can choose not to provide this additional information.

Q28 We willen in deze studie de relatie tussen groen in de woonomgeving en welzijn onderzoeken. Op grond van luchtfoto's beschikken we over informatie over hoeveel groen er precies in uw woonomgeving aanwezig is. Om die informatie aan de door u verstrekte gegevens te kunnen koppelen, moeten we wel weten waar u woont. Omdat dit gevoelige informatie is, nemen we extra veiligheidsmaatregelen. Deze adresinformatie wordt apart van de andere gegevens opgeslagen en alleen even gekoppeld om de luchtfoto-gegevens op te halen die we voor de analyse gebruiken. U kunt er uiteraard voor kiezen om deze gegevens niet te verstrekken.

Q29 Please input your four-digit postcode.

- Four-digit postcode: _____
- Prefer not to disclose

Q29 Voer uw 4-cijferige postcode in.

- 4-cijferige postcode: _____
 - Wil ik niet zeggen
-

Q30 Please input the two letters following the four digits of your postcode.

- Two letters in postcode: _____
- Prefer not to disclose

Q30 Voer de 2 letters van uw postcode.

- 2 letters van uw postcode: _____
 - Wil ik niet zeggen
-

Q31 Please input your house number.

- House number: _____
- Prefer not to disclose

Q31 Voer uw huisnummer in.

- Huisnummer: _____
 - Wil ik niet zeggen
-

Page Break

End of Block: Address
